

Application of the REPAS methodology to analyse the reliability of the EHRs in the decay heat removal strategy for an SMR

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ABSTRACT

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), particularly Light Water-SMRs (LW-SMR), represent a viable option for near-term deployment of nuclear technology in Europe, building upon established Light Water Reactor technology while incorporating evolutionary design modifications like passive safety systems. While these systems offer advantages, such as independence from external power for the operation and component minimization, they face potential functional failures due to natural circulation mechanism. Therefore, such failure modes must be systematically addressed in SMR design and safety reviews. Current guidance on passive safety system requirements and failure mode modelling needs consolidation. Therefore, short-term research priorities for SMR deployment include reliability analysis of thermal-hydraulic phenomena that drive passive system operation, as well as related uncertainty quantification. Building on ENEA's MELCOR input-deck of a generic SMR of about 300 MWe, developed within the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA (Safety Analysis of SMR with Passive Mitigation Strategies-Severe Accident) project, this work applies the REPAS (Reliability Evaluation of Passive Safety Systems) methodology to the Emergency Heat Removal System (EHRs), a key passive safety system for decay heat removal in advanced designs. REPAS will help analyses various system states, including low-probability scenarios, to understand EHRs behaviour and its impact on plant safety.

KEYWORDS

REPAS, EHRs, Passive System, SMR, DBA

1. INTRODUCTION

The safety of Nuclear Power Plants (NPP) is a key element in advancing nuclear technology. As nuclear energy continues to play a crucial role in the global energy mix, its acceptance is based on reliable safety measures that minimize or eliminate radiological risks to the external environment. Strict regulatory oversight and comprehensive safety assessments including accident simulations are essential to maintaining public trust and ensuring compliance with national and international safety standards.

Light Water-SMRs (LW-SMR), particularly integral Pressurized Water Reactor (iPWR), are ready to be licensed as new builds and, therefore, represent a promising advancement in nuclear technology. The layout of this reactor type takes as reference the operational plant experience and the feedback of the established Light Water Reactor (LWR) designs, incorporating design modifications to increase the inherent safety of the plant such as the usage of passive safety systems to reduce the reliance on external power sources and active components.

In this context, while passive safety systems reduce the reliance on external power sources and active components, their performance depends primarily on natural physical phenomena—such as gravity-driven flow. These natural mechanisms, however, are sensitive to scenario-specific conditions and operational uncertainties that can affect their ability to fulfill safety functions as expected. Of particular concern is the so-called *functional failure*, which refers to the failure of passive systems to operate as expected due to limitations in natural driving forces, even in the absence of any mechanical or electrical malfunction. Therefore, deterministic characterization of these conditions is essential to ensure the robustness, predictability, and overall reliability of passive systems for an effective safety demonstration. A core methodology to address this challenge is the REPAS [1] [2]; it integrates deterministic and probabilistic analyses to assess failure probabilities of passive safety systems under various scenarios. This methodology leveraging computational codes which allows the simulation of reactor behaviour in transient scenario, including design extension conditions, enables a systematic assessment of the performance of passive systems and their potential failure modes.

The reference design of the present work is based on a generic design developed along the Horizon Euratom SASPAM project [3] [4] called Design 2, which is characterized by the use of several passive systems, a dry containment and a power of about 300 [MWe] [5]. One of the main passive safety features of the selected designs is the adoption of the Emergency Heat Removal Systems (EHRS), designed to manage decay heat removal during accident conditions.

This paper presents a preliminary application of the REPAS methodology on a generic iPWR type SMR, which, making use of the MELCOR [6] [7] code for deterministic simulations, aims firstly to identify the main parameters that go to influence the proper operation of the EHRS and secondly to highlight the importance of its role among the safety demonstration procedures in SMRs.

2. RELIABILITY EVALUATION OF PASSIVE SAFETY SYSTEMS (REPAS)

The Reliability Evaluation of Passive Safety Systems (REPAS) methodology was developed in the late 1990s through a cooperative effort by ENEA, the University of Pisa, the Polytechnic of Milan, and the University of Rome. This methodology is based on the evaluation of the failure probability of a passive system to perform its desired function, considering the uncertainties of the physical and geometric parameters that can cause the failure of the expected thermal-hydraulic phenomena and, consequently, the passive safety system. The general objective of REPAS is to analytically characterize the performance of a passive system to ensure its correct operation, compare the performance of passive and active systems, and compare different passive systems. The roadmap of the adopted methodology is illustrated in **Figure 1** and summarized in the following key points, using the figure as a reference.

Figure 1. Flow diagram of the REPAS methodology [2] [8].

The initial stage of the procedure is to select the passive system, then proceed as follows:

- i. Define the Target Mission (TM) of the passive system and identify the relevant phenomenology involved. The parameters defining the operation and transient behaviour of the passive system must be selected (one might consider the velocities of the liquid and steam, the heat transfer coefficient in each zone of the system, or the local values of pressure, temperature, etc.). It is important to note that a procedure based on expert judgment is required to identify and select the relevant parameters of the system.
- ii. Define the Failure Criteria (FC) of the system. For the evaluation of FC is essential to understand the system design objectives so the TM of the passive system must be carefully considered during this process. FC can be defined as specific single-value targets or as functions of time, potentially varying with environmental conditions where the passive system operates. Additionally, these criteria may change during a transient.
- iii. Identify related and root causes. A systematic process is necessary to ensure that all possible causes of failure are properly addressed. This can be achieved through a hierarchical structure or the more common Fault Tree and the Event Tree methods. If the passive system is part of a larger and more complex system, the entire system must be considered.
- iv. Decomposition of the phenomena occurring (or assumed to occur) in the system into the relevant fundamental parameters of the system.
- v. Ranking of most important parameters. A generic passive system may function under steady-state conditions or during transients so considering all parameters may be impractical for computational purposes. Thus, a classification process is necessary, which may include grouping similar parameters.
- vi. Screening of the less important parameters. In this step the goal is to reduce the number of design and critical parameters.
- vii. Identification of parameter relationship and dependencies. Within this step, physical constraints and stochastic dependencies between the selected parameters should be highlighted.

- viii. Detailed code modelling. It is important to develop a detailed system model through qualified computational tool.
- ix. Nominal case evaluation. An acceptable reference system behaviour results from either an appropriate experiment or a best-estimate code prediction, with the latter often being the only practical approach in many situations. Consequently, it is necessary to determine a reference transient and complete a best-estimate prediction for it.
- x. Assignment or updating of probability distributions. For the passive system under consideration, each operational state and critical parameter value should be assigned a certain occurrence probability. This involves assigning probability distributions, including ranges of variations and PDFs, for all parameters identified in step (vii).
- xi. Probability propagation and analysis. Once the PDFs (or discrete probability values) along with the variation ranges for the selected parameters have been established, the main target is how these results help determine the reliability of the system in question. Since conduct comprehensive sensitivity studies is impractical even for the simplest system, it is necessary to find the minimum number of code runs (transient scenarios of the system) that provide sufficient information about the overall system performance (incorporating system reliability). One way to address this need is through the use of Wilks' formula [9] [10] that can provide the minimum number of calculations needed to characterize system performance. For cases where only one Figure Of Merit (FOM) is being examined, the required number of code runs N , for a one-sided tolerance interval, is determined by the desired probability α and confidence level β , as shown in equation (1):

$$1 - \alpha^N = \beta \quad (1)$$

If more than one FOM is investigated the required number of code runs can be found by solving the following equation (2) [11]:

$$\beta = \sum_{j=0}^{N-p} \frac{N!}{j!(N-j)!} \alpha^j (1 - \alpha)^{N-j} \quad (2)$$

where p represents the number of FOMs.

- xii. Reliability evaluation. At this point of the methodology an 'analytical' comparison is made between the results of the N transient scenarios and the reference/target system performance, considering the FC defined in step (ii). This procedure generates FOMs for the system, where the probability of system failure is reported as a function of the probability of an assigned scenario occurring. These characteristics are specific to the chosen system and can be used to assess the system's acceptability and to compare it with other systems.

3. REFERENCE DESIGN AND CALCULATION

The iPWR considered in the present REPAS application is a generic 300 MWe SMR type. The selected layout (**Figure 2**), has been used in the framework of the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project, and it is known as Design 2. Such design was chosen to represent a relatively high-power SMR and to evaluate the role and interaction of different passive systems in the accident mitigation strategy.

Figure 2. Generic Design 2 layout.

Figure 3. MELCOR CVH nodalization developed by SNAP.

It is characterized by the use of several passive systems and a dry containment (or DryWell-DW) The layout consists of an integral Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV), which contains the core, a compact Steam Generator (SG), the Control Rod Drive Mechanism (CRDM), the primary pumps and the pressurizer (PRZ) included in the upper head. Moreover, the passive safety systems considered in the design are: EHRS, Automatic Depressurization System (ADS), Emergency Borated Tank (EBT), Pressure Suppression System (PSS), Long-term Gravity Make-up System (LGMS), flooding of the Reactor Cavity (RC). In normal operation the reactor operates in forced circulation while employs a passive mitigation strategy in accidental transients.

The code used to develop the input-deck and perform the methodology is the Severe Accident (SA) integral code MELCOR. It is developed by Sandia National Laboratories (SNL) for the United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission (USNRC) and is capable of simulating thermal-hydraulic phenomena under both steady-state and transient conditions, as well as the degradation phenomena affecting the RPV, RC, and containment of a LWR during a postulated SA. Integral SA codes like MELCOR are widely used for independent analysis for supporting safety review for current and advanced designs. Recent activities within the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project [3][4] have independently demonstrated MELCOR's capability to predict natural circulation thermal-hydraulic phenomena in iPWR designs employing passive safety systems, confirming its suitability for use in this methodology. The nodalization has been developed using the Symbolic Nuclear Analysis Package (SNAP) [14].

In order to develop the MELCOR input-deck (**Figure 3**) a reference database was needed; therefore, considering the reactor features and the passive systems selected (Passive decay heat removal, Primary automatic depressurization, Passive high-pressure safety injection, Containment pressure suppression, Passive low-pressure safety injection and Flooding of the Reactor Cavity), a generic IRIS SMR type has been considered as reference of the nodalization and no proprietary data have been used. Moreover, the main geometric information has been determined by scaling the data available from the SPES-3 facility [15] [16] [17], by engineering evaluation or public general data available for the IRIS reactor [12] [13]. The nodalization was developed by ENEA along the SASPAM-SA project (**Figure 3**).

The reference calculation concerns a Loss Of Coolant Accident (LOCA) scenario [18]. Specifically, the selected scenario for the transient analysis is the double-ended guillotine break of one of the two Direct vessel Injection (DVI) lines considering the availability of all the passive safety systems. This is one of the most challenging scenarios in relation to the safety of the plant. At the end of the transient regarding the main FOMs the minimum normalized core level predicted by the code is about 0.6 m with the top of the core partially uncovered for about 17000 s, while the maximum predicted casing temperature is 622 K. Under these conditions at the end of the calculation, no core degradation and neither hydrogen production phenomena are observed. Further information about the reference calculation phenomenology can be found in [18].

4. APPLICATION OF THE METHODOLOGY

In this work, the REPAS methodology is used to analyse the EHRS system and its impact on the long-term core cooling function. For the current REPAS application, three FC have been identified based on the results of the reference calculations:

1. Maximum cladding temperature. In the reference calculation, the final cladding temperature is approximately 400 K (**Figure 4**).
FC 1 - Cladding temperature > 600 K after the activation of the EHRS.
2. RPV collapsed level. In the reference calculation, the final RPV collapsed coolant level is above the Top Active Fuel (TAF) (**Figure 6**).
FC 2 - RPV collapsed coolant level < 1/2 of the active core after the activation of the EHRS.
3. Power removed by EHRS. In the reference calculation, the initial power removed by EHRS is more than 100 MW (**Figure 8**).
FC 3 - Power removed by EHRS < 70 MW at the activation of the system.

It is important to emphasize that in this work, the FC definitions are not associated with engineering or safety limits. Instead, they are defined based on the reference calculation solely for the purpose of applying the REPAS methodology showing its applicability to a full reactor and not to a single component extrapolated. Once the TM of the system was defined, i.e., “the removal of decay power from the core to an external heat sink”, some key parameters that could affect the operation of the passive system were identified and selected: **1.** Loss coefficient; **2.** Surface roughness; **3.** Valve opening ratio (VOR); **4.** Non-Condensable Gas (NCG) fraction; **5.** Pool initial level.

Parameters, ranges, and PDFs are detailed in Table 1. Defining these values is crucial for assessing the probability of occurrence for each system configuration, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of system performance and potential failure. For the probabilistic calculations, 150 simulations were performed, exceeding the minimum of 124 runs determined by the application of Eq. (2), to account for any potential calculation failures. Further clarification is required regarding the sampling method used for the fraction of NCG. Due to the method of entering input data into the code, it was not possible to directly sample the amount of NCG. Since the initial quantity of NCG inside the EHRS tubes affect the initial amount of water, the variable used for sampling this parameter was the initial water level in the

EHRS. Therefore, a high value in the liquid level in EHRS Heat-Exchangers (EHRS-HXs) corresponds to a low percentage of NCG vice versa a low value in the level indicates a high presence of NCG.

Table 1. Selected parameters for the REPAS probabilistic code calculations

Parameter	Reference value	PDF
Loss coefficient	0.6	1% $1.14 \leq x < 1.2$
		2% $1.08 \leq x < 1.14$
		17% $0.9 \leq x < 1.08$
		80% $0.6 \leq x < 0.9$
Surface roughness	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m	6.56% $4.75 \cdot 10^{-5} \leq x < 4.875 \cdot 10^{-5}$
		86.88% $4.875 \cdot 10^{-5} \leq x < 5.125 \cdot 10^{-5}$
		6.56% $5.125 \cdot 10^{-5} \leq x < 5.25 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Valve opening ratio	1.0	1% $0.0 \leq x < 0.05$
		2% $0.05 \leq x < 0.1$
		17% $0.1 \leq x < 0.5$
		80% $0.5 \leq x < 1.0$
Heat-exchanger initial level (parameter connected to NCG)	0.1667 m	1% $0.0 \leq x < 8.335 \cdot 10^{-3}$
		2% $8.335 \cdot 10^{-3} \leq x < 1.667 \cdot 10^{-2}$
		17% $1.667 \cdot 10^{-2} \leq x < 8.335 \cdot 10^{-2}$
		80% $8.335 \cdot 10^{-2} \leq x < 1.667 \cdot 10^{-1}$
Pool initial level	2 m	1% $1.25 \leq x < 1.2875$
		2% $1.2875 \leq x < 1.325$
		17% $1.325 \leq x < 1.625$
		80% $1.625 \leq x < 2.0$

To simplify the determination of ranges and probabilities, discrete values have been selected, with a central value representing the nominal condition in the reference case. Parameter ranges extend to values above and below the reference value, and limits set based on the physical configuration of the operation of the passive system (e.g. valve full open and close, pool maximum level and minimum level that uncover the HX, etc) [19]. Discrete probability distributions are assigned to the defined ranges, with the nominal value receiving the highest probability, and lower probabilities assigned to values further from it.

5. RESULTS

As mentioned above, a total of 150 Monte Carlo simulations were performed to explore the range of input parameter uncertainties relevant to the EHRS. However, due to numerical failures, 24 runs were not considered and therefore only 126 runs were conducted in the analysis (still exceeding the minimum number of 124 required by Eq. (2) for the robustness of the thermal hydraulic reliability analysis to be guaranteed). Each run was defined by random draws from parameter distributions governing the Valve Opening Ratio (VOR), NCG fraction, initial pool level, and other potentially influential variables. Additionally, a purely deterministic calculation was conducted to represent an extreme case within the parameter variation range, addressing a low-probability scenario that otherwise would not have been captured by probabilistic sampling.

5.1. Probabilistic Calculations

To assess the EHRS's ability to manage a LOCA scenario, the three FC shown in *Section 4* were adopted. FC1 has been exceeded by seven probabilistic calculations (**Figure 5**), with six of these runs significantly exceeding the chosen value by the end of the simulation.

Figure 4. Reference calculation cladding temperature versus time.

Figure 5. REPAS Maximum cladding temperatures versus time.

Figure 6. Reference calculation RPV collapsed coolant level versus time.

Figure 7. REPAS Minimum RPV collapsed coolant levels versus time.

However, two runs reach at the end 700 K, suggesting further analysis and a longer simulation time to deeply understand the transient evolution. FC2 has been exceeded by five probabilistic calculations (**Figure 7**), and it is important to note that whenever FC2 is satisfied, the remaining FCs are also fulfilled. FC3 has been exceeded by twenty-three probabilistic calculations (**Figure 9**). In sixteen of these runs, this is the only FC encountered, while the other simulations correspond to those already mentioned.

It is good to note how the mentioned plots, particularly for cladding temperature (**Figure 5**) and core level (**Figure 7**), show that the reference case is not centered within the uncertainty band of probabilistic cases. These results come from the definition of input parameters and their value ranges; in fact, except for surface roughness, none have their nominal value centered, leading to consistently worse scenarios respect the reference one.

Figure 8. Reference calculation Power removed by EHRs versus time.

Figure 9. REPAS Maximum power removed by EHRs versus time.

5.2. Deterministic Calculation

To apply and test the methodology a deterministic simulation was introduced to account for low-probability or boundary range condition not captured by probabilistic sampling of the input uncertainty parameters. Specifically in this first application, it addressed the case of a VOR equal to zero, representing an extreme within the parameter's variation range that have not been sampled in the probabilistic analyses. This simulation results in a Beyond Design Basis Accident (BDBA) scenario that leads to a SA. In fact, with the EHRs system inactive and no heat removal from the RPV, steam is released into the DW after the ADS-1 valve is opened, causing a significant increase in pressure until the maximum design pressure is reached. Subsequently, there is the opening of the containment valves directly connected to the environment simulating a containment break [20] due to the high pressure (in the used input no Filter Venting System has been considered because no evaluation on the radiological consequences are performed). Therefore, due to a delay in the Low DP RPV-Containment signal [18], the water loss from the DVI break is not reduced quickly enough to prevent the core uncovering at the beginning the transient. The inability to cool the uncovered core (despite EBT injection into the intact line) led to the degradation and the cladding failure.

5.3. Uncertainty and Sensitive Analysis

In the following **Figure 10** and **Figure 11**, maximum cladding temperature and maximum power removed after the onset of NC in the EHRs are respectively plotted against their probability of occurrence, with the deterministic case represented by a black dot. Analysing the relative probabilities of different simulations, it was observed that some specific runs fully achieved the TM despite having a very low probability of occurrence.

Figure 10. Maximum cladding temperature as a function of the occurrence probability.

Figure 11. Maximum power removed by EHRS as a function of the occurrence.

Figure 12. Spearman's correlation coefficient for maximum cladding temperature.

Figure 13. Spearman's correlation coefficient for maximum power removed by EHRS.

This can be explained by the influence of the loss coefficient and surface roughness parameters in those runs. In fact, in these simulations, the values of these parameters were sampled far from their nominal values, resulting in a very low probability of occurrence. However, since these parameters have less impact on the FOMs than others, the transient behaviour in these cases does not significantly deviate from the reference case. Consequently, although their occurrence probability is low, their impact on system reliability still minimal. To support the previous considerations, **Figure 12 - Figure 13** show the Spearman correlation coefficient for cladding temperature and power removed by EHRS, respectively calculated at the same observation time of the FOMs. Spearman's correlation measures the strength and direction of a monotonic relationship between input variables and system responses by ranking data. Its coefficient ranges from -1 to +1: a value of +1 indicates perfectly increasing monotonic relationship, while -1 indicates a perfectly decreasing monotonic relationship. A value of 0 indicates no monotonic relationship between the variables, while other intermediate values reflect weaker monotonic relationships. To perform this uncertainty analysis, a Python script called "Python Uncertainty tool" developed by ENEA and University of Palermo along the MUSA project was used [21] [22].

The analysis highlights the key parameters influencing system performance. The NCG fraction has a significant negative impact, reducing cooling efficiency. The VOR plays a crucial role, with higher values improving coolant retention, enhancing power removal, and reducing cladding temperature. In contrast, the EHRS loss coefficient and surface roughness show minimal influence across all metrics.

Thus, observing the results, NCG fraction and VOR are the most critical parameters in determining system reliability and safety.

As mentioned in Section 4, the amount of NCG was measured starting from the liquid level in the EHRS-HXs volumes, where a higher coolant level corresponds to a lower presence of NCG. Therefore, in the Spearman diagrams the relationships between the various FOMs and the NCG must be interpreted inversely, i.e., what appears to be a relationship of increasing monotonicity is actually a relationship of decreasing monotonicity and vice versa. These findings underscore that NCG fraction and VOR are the most critical parameters for ensuring system reliability and safety. Table 2 shows the probabilities of occurrence for each individual FC, as well as the probability of meet at least one of the three FCs.

Table 2. Probability of occurrence of FC1, FC2, FC3 and of, at least, one FC.

Event	Value
P_{FC1}	$8.69 \cdot 10^{-3}$
P_{FC2}	$4.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$
P_{FC3}	$9.22 \cdot 10^{-2}$
P_{oneFC}	$9.22 \cdot 10^{-2}$

Figure 14. Stability Map.

Using the occurrence probabilities from each code run, the probability for each FC was obtained by considering only those runs in which that specific FC was satisfied. As anticipated from previous results, FC3 shows the highest probability of occurrence, while FC1 and FC2 show lower probabilities. To conclude this section, it is shown the Stability Map (**Figure 14**) that plots the core water level against the cladding temperature for a range of probabilistic simulations, with each marker sized according to the power removed by the EHRS (larger markers represent greater heat exchange).

The horizontal red line (FC1) marks the 600 K temperature limit while the vertical green line (FC2) indicates the minimum acceptable water level. Points appearing above the red line or to the left of the green line exceed these respective thresholds. Therefore, four distinct regions emerge from these boundaries:

- Green Area (Stable): Cladding temperature remains under 600 K, and water level stays above the critical threshold.

- Red Area (Unstable): Cladding temperature exceeds 600 K, and the water level is insufficient.
- Upper Yellow Area: Adequate water level but temperatures above 600 K, suggesting heat removal issues despite sufficient water.
- Lower Yellow Area: Cladding temperature is within limits, but the water level falls below the threshold, raising long-term cooling concerns.

The deterministic calculation appears as the leftmost and highest point on the graph; it fails all three FCs by exhibiting extremely high temperatures and dangerously low water levels. Overall, **Figure 14** provides a clear indication of how various scenarios perform in terms of safety, highlighting the regions where system stability is maintained and where it is compromised.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The EHRS passive system plays a key role in the mitigation strategy of reactor designs using passive safety systems, as iPWR. In this paper, the REPAS methodology was applied to a full generic iPWR having as a focus the EHRS performance, with the aim of evaluating its reliability under appropriate assumptions through a probabilistic-deterministic approach. The analysis was performed having as a reference a DBA scenario in which a double-ended guillotine break of a DVI line have been postulated in a generic iPWR of about 300 [MWe]. Through the MELCOR code, 150 simulations were conducted with input parameter sets sampled through the Monte Carlo method and one deterministic-type simulation in which the complete failure of the EHRS system ($VOR = 0\%$) was assumed (worst case) since was not sampled by the Monte Carlo method. The results of the application have shown:

- The effective applicability of the REPAS methodology to the EHRS and not specifically issue have been identified along the application;
- The needs of specific deterministic calculations in analysing low-probability or boundary system states that may not be captured in probabilistic analysis;
- Functional failure of the EHRS and related probability occurs under specific conditions: very low valve opening ratios, high concentrations of non-condensable gases, and low RWST levels, which compromise FC1 and FC2.

As indicated by the uncertainty analysis, the characterization of input uncertainty parameters significantly influences the reliability analysis outcomes. Consequently, careful attention must be paid to the selection of PDFs and parameter ranges, ensuring that they are grounded in reliable references or sound engineering judgment. Typically, a combination of experimental data, analytical findings, and expert input is essential [21]. The PDFs should be categorized into more specific values, with a more detailed analysis accompanying the selection process; therefore, future studies should prioritize the careful selection of PDFs and parameter ranges based on solid references and expert insight.

NOMENCLATURE

ADS: Automatic Depressurization System; **BDBA:** Beyond Design Basis Accident; **CRDM:** Control Rod Drive Mechanism; **CV:** Control Volume; **DVI:** Direct Vessel Injection; **DW:** Drywell; **EBT:** Emergency Boration Tank; **EHRS:** Emergency Heat Removal System; **FC:** Failure Criteria; **FOM:** Figure Of Merit; **HX:** Heat Exchanger; **iPWR:** integral-Pressurized Water Reactor; **LGMS:** Long-term Gravity Make-up System; **LOCA:** Loss Of Coolant Accident; **LWR:** Light Water Reactor; **LW-SMR:** Light Water SMR; **NC:** Natural Circulation; **NCG:** Non-Condensable Gas; **NPP:** Nuclear Power Plant; **PDF:** Probability Density Function; **PRZ:** Pressurizer; **PSS:** Pressure Suppression System; **RC:** Reactor Cavity; **REPAS:** Reliability Evaluation of Passive Safety Systems; **RWST:** Refuelling Water Storage Tank; **RPV:** Reactor Pressure Vessel; **SA:** Severe Accident; **SG:** Steam Generator; **SMR:** Small Modular Reactor; **SNAP:** Symbolic Nuclear Analysis Package; **SNL:** Sandia National Laboratory; **TAF:** Top Active Fuel; **TM:** Target Mission; **USNRC:** United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission; **VOR:** Valve Opening Ratio.

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